

A Multifaceted Approach to Evaluating Field Operation Training

Lin Wang¹, Chin Fang Weng¹, Matthew Virgile¹, Thomas Mathew^{1,2}

¹U.S. Census Bureau, 4600 Silver Hill Rd, Suitland, MD 20746

²University of Maryland, Baltimore County, 1000 Hilltop Cir, Baltimore, MD 21250

Abstract

Field operation training is an essential component of large-scale, in-person data collection such as the 2020 Census Nonresponse Followup (NRFU) operation. The effectiveness of such training has a direct consequence on the quality of data collected in the operation. A question is thus raised: How to evaluate effectiveness of a field operation training in a real-world setting where only limited operational data are available? In the present study, we developed a multifaceted approach to evaluating training effectiveness through generating convergent evidence. This approach can be summarized as five steps: (1) comprehending the operational process, (2) defining evaluation goals and developing evaluation strategies, (3) identifying available data sources and defining outcome measures, (4) conducting training effectiveness analyses through multiple outcome measures, and (5) drawing conclusions based on evidence obtained from the analyses. In this paper, we will use the evaluation of 2020 Census NRFU training as a case study to disseminate our training evaluation approach. Our evaluation started with a comprehensive review of the NRFU operational process, followed by developing primary and secondary field performance indicators based on available operational data. Evaluation data sets were constructed through linking the training assessment data and field performance data. Statistical methods were explored to investigate the association between training and field performance. This multifaceted approach demonstrates how training evaluation in an operational setting can be carried out with limited data sources.

Key Words: Census, training, assessment, Nonresponse Followup, NRFU, trend test

1. Introduction

Field operation training is an essential requirement of a large-scale, in-person data collection. The effectiveness of such training has a direct consequence on the quality of data collected in the operation. Conducting evaluation of training programs is a widely practiced means to assure or improve training effectiveness. Training evaluations are generally carried out at one or some of the four levels (Kirkpatrick & Kirkpatrick, 2006): (1) Reaction - What did the trainees feel about the training experience (e.g., satisfaction with training)? (2) Learning - What knowledge did the trainees have obtained? (3) Behavior - How did trainees apply their training in the field? (4) Results - What was the impact on operation? The evaluation at the results-level is most important because it provides the ultimate assessment of training effectiveness. However, results-level training evaluations have been rarely conducted because of difficulty in data collection and high cost (Hope et al, 2024). One question is thus raised: how to evaluate effectiveness of a field operation training at the results level in a real world setting where only limited operational data are available? In the present study, we developed a systematic and multifaceted approach to generating convergent evidence of training effectiveness. This approach involves five steps: (1) comprehending the operational process, (2) defining evaluation goals and developing evaluation strategies, (3) identifying available data sources and defining outcome measures, (4) conducting training effectiveness analyses through multiple outcome measures, and (5) drawing conclusions based on

evidence obtained from the analyses. In the following we will use the evaluation of the training program for the 2020 Census Nonresponse Followup (NRFU) operation as a case study to disseminate our training evaluation approach.

2. Comprehension of NRFU Operation

To effectively carry out an evaluation of a field operation training, it is essential for the evaluation researchers to comprehend the operation and training processes. We thus conducted an in-depth review of the NRFU operation. In NRFU, enumerators visited housing units at addresses that had not provided responses to the 2020 Census to determine the status of the housing units (occupied or vacant) and to enumerate housing units that were occupied on Census Day (April 1) (Gibb et al, 2023). The NRFU operation has historically been the largest and most expensive field operation of the decennial census. The NRFU operation involved three phases: enumerator training, field data collection (production), and quality control (monitoring data collection quality and making intervention as needed). All enumerator candidates first received training and took an assessment of knowledge and skills acquired through training. Those who passed the training assessment were sent to the field to conduct NRFU. In the middle of the NRFU production, the quality control operation began.

2.1 NRFU Training and Assessment

The U.S. Census Bureau developed a training program to prepare potential enumerators for the NRFU production. Prior to commencing the NRFU production, each potential enumerator received 16 hours of online training and 14 hours of classroom training (Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, classroom training was re-purposed into self-study followed by a conference call). The training covered field procedures, interview skills, data quality, operational efficiency, and operating the data collection device. The training was conducted in a combination of online and in-person modes. At the end of the training, each trainee took a 15-item assessment. The assessment covered knowledge and skills in the following areas: interview skills, communication with non-English speaker, operational procedures, understanding of NRFU operation, and quality control. All the response options for the 15 items were multiple choices. Based on subject-matter experts' judgement of the impacts and the relative costs of correcting incorrect responses for each item, eight items were assigned a weight of 5 (high impact and cost), six items a weight of 3 (medium impact and cost), and one item a weight of 2 (low impact and cost) (Table 1). An aggregated weighted score, normalized to between 0 and 100 (inclusive), was assigned to each assessment (Tuttle & Virgile, 2019). A cut-off score of 70 was used such that enumerators with a score less than 70 would conduct NRFU under supervisory observation until their performance became satisfactory while others would conduct NRFU independently.

Table 1: Weighting Scheme for the Assessment Items

Importance category	High	Medium	Low	TOTAL
Number of items	8	6	1	15
Weight	5	3	2	
Areas of knowledge and skills	interview skills, communication with non-English speaker, operational procedures, understanding of NRFU operation, quality control	interview skills, communication with non-English speaker, operational procedures, understanding of NRFU operation	operational procedures	
Total weighted value	40	18	2	60
% weighted value	66.67%	30.00%	3.33%	100.00%

2.2 NRFU Production

The 2020 Census NRFU production (data collection) was carried out by trained enumerators. NRFU cases included the cases of interviewing households, cases of visiting managers of multiunit structures, and cases of verifying addresses for Census self-responses without a Census ID. The present evaluation is limited to only the cases of interviewing households. During household interviews, enumerators used the Field Data Capture (FDC) application on an iPhone to determine housing unit occupancy and to conduct interviews if possible. The enumerators collected information on the number of people who lived at the housing unit on Census Day (April 1st), their demographic characteristics and relationship to the respondent, tenure (owner/renter) of the housing unit, and data related to the interview process (e.g., the length of the interview).

2.3 NRFU Quality Control Operation

A subset of completed NRFU cases underwent a second interview (re-interview, RI) for quality control. The same enumerators who worked on production cases conducted RI on cases that they didn't work in production. While conducting RI, enumerators were aware of conducting RI instead of initial interview, and generally followed the same procedures for RI cases as production (and consequently, in general, the same type of information as in the production cases was collected). Using data collected from RI as a benchmark, the data collected from a production case were compared with its corresponding RI case. The comparison was first performed by a computer algorithm and followed by, if needed, a human examination. The comparison produced one of three outcomes: Pass, Fail, or Hard Fail. "Pass" was defined as, compared to the RI case outcome of the same address, the production case was determined as having been completed correctly or showing insufficient evidence of having been completed incorrectly; "Fail" as the enumerator having committed an error in the case (e.g., undercounting household members) but not making deliberate falsification; and "Hard Fail" as a deliberate falsification being committed in the case and its enumerator being fired.

Figure 1: The composition of NRFU cases. Ineligible cases include incomplete cases and complete cases that have been validated through comparison to administrative data.

RI cases were selected from eligible NRFU production cases using four methods: Random Selection, Analytic Selection, Supplemental Selection, and Rework Selection (Tau et al, 2023). Eligible NRFU production cases were those that were completed but their quality had not been verified. In the Random Selection, RI cases were systematically sampled from eligible production cases such that, for each enumerator, one of the first three eligible production cases was randomly selected and then every 40th case thereafter was selected. RI cases sampled through the Random Selection amounted to 2.5% of all eligible NRFU cases. In the Analytic Selection, a computer algorithm ran a battery of checks on the enumerator's behaviors and his/her NRFU case quality,

looking for indications of falsification, for example, a case was completed much quicker than usual. If a particular case or enumerator surpassed the threshold of falsification indication, the case or the enumerator's next two eligible cases would be selected for RI. In the Supplemental Selection, trained clerks selected additional cases for RI to further examine a particular enumerator's work quality if the clerks felt uncertain about the enumerator's performance, for example, unusual number of vacant addresses. In the Rework Selection, when an enumerator was determined to have committed data falsification, all of his/her eligible cases, that had not undergone RI, were selected. All RI cases selected through the four methods were mutually exclusive. See Figure 1 for the composition of NRFU cases. For the details of the NRFU QC operation, see the publication by Tau et al (2023).

3. Developing Working Hypothesis and Strategies for NRFU Training Evaluation

The basic goal of this evaluation was to assess the effectiveness of the 2020 Census NRFU operation training. To do so, we developed a model of causal relationships (Figure 2): The potential enumerators would first receive training; effective training would result in good training assessment scores; given that training assessment scores do reflect enumerators' competence of knowledge and skills, better training assessment scores should lead to better field performance.

Figure 2: The model of causal relationships between training and field performance.

Informed by the processes of NRFU training, production, and quality control, we developed the following strategies for the present evaluation: (1) The evaluation was to be based on the assumption that training assessment scores reflect enumerators' level of knowledge and skills acquired during training. (2) Based on the model in Figure 2, we formulated a working hypothesis that an enumerator's training assessment score would be positively associated to his/her work competence, in other words, the higher the assessment score, the more competent the enumerator would be and consequently the better the data collection quality. (3) The evaluation was to be limited to enumerators who had a weighted training assessment score of 70 or above because enumerators with a score less than 70 received additional supervisory help in the field which could confound the training effect. (4) Random-selection RI outcome was to be used as the primary indicator of enumerators' field performance because it was the only dataset that would be representative to the population of all eligible cases. (5) Multiple data sources were to be used to seek convergent evidence of training effectiveness.

4. Identifying Data Sources and Defining Outcome Measures

Two types of data were identified as essential for the evaluation: NRFU enumerator training assessment score data and NRFU RI case data.

The training assessment data were collected at the person level. Each trainee had one record of assessment. The assessment record included the following information: trainee ID, outcome from each of 15 assessment items (correct or incorrect), and weighted total score (sum of weighted item score, normalized between 0 and 100). Table 2 shows the distribution of RI-eligible enumerators across the weighted assessment scores. In the present training evaluation, data of about 150,000 enumerators were included in the dataset of enumerator training assessment.

RI data were collected at the household level (RI case) and divided into four subsets: data collected through Random Selection (Random), Analytic Selection (Analytic), Supplemental Selection (Supplemental), or Rework Selection (Rework). Distribution of RI cases through the four selection

types for all enumerators is shown in Figure 3. For the present evaluation, the following information was collected for each RI case: household ID, enumerator ID who conducted initial production interview (not RI), and RI outcome (Pass/Fail (Hard Fail was merged into Fail)).

Weighted assessment score	<70	70-75	76-80	81-85	86-90	91-95	96-100	Total
Number of enumerators	14,500	8,600	13,000	18,000	19,500	23,000	54,500	151,100
Percent of enumerators	9.6%	5.7%	8.6%	11.9%	12.9%	15.2%	36.1%	100.0%

Note: Enumerator count data presented here are rounded to 100, 500, or 1000, depending on quantity, to avoid identity disclosure.

Figure 3: The distribution of RI cases by selection type for all enumerators.

The training assessment data and RI data were linked through enumerator ID. Based on the nature of available data sources, we defined one primary performance measure and three secondary performance measures at the sample level, as described below:

Primary performance measure:

RI pass rate of the 1st Randomly-selected case = (# of enumerators with the 1st randomly-selected RI case passed) / (Total # of enumerators with the 1st randomly-selected RI case)

Secondary performance measures:

- Rate of enumerators with RI cases selected through Analytic = (# of enumerators with RI cases selected through Analytic) / (Total # of RI-eligible enumerators)
- Rate of enumerators with RI cases selected through Supplemental = (# of enumerators with RI cases selected through Supplemental) / (Total # of RI-eligible enumerators)
- Rate of enumerators with RI cases selected through Rework = (# of enumerators with RI cases selected through Rework) / (Total # of RI-eligible enumerators)

Higher RI pass rate of the 1st Randomly-selected case suggests better field performance while lower rates of enumerators with RI cases selected through Analytic, Supplemental, or Rework suggest better field performance.

5. Data Analysis – Methods and Results

In this section, we report our analyses and results to address the basic question concerning training effectiveness: How is the training assessment score associated with the field performance? In this analysis, the weighted total training assessment score was used to predict the field performance. It was assumed that the assessment scores reflect enumerators' knowledge and skills acquired through

training in a monotonic fashion, i.e., the higher the assessment score, the better command of knowledge and skills. The outcome of randomly-selected RI was used as the primary indicator of field performance for the reasons stated in Section 3. The *Cochran-Armitage Test for Trend* (Cochran, 1954; Armitage, 1955) was performed to assess the effect of NRFU training assessment score on field performance. The Cochran-Armitage test is a modified version of the Pearson chi-squared test that incorporates a suspected ordering in the effects of a categorical predictor on the outcome variable. The test statistic is formulated as follows:

$$z^2 = \frac{[\sum_{j=1}^k y_j (x_j - \bar{x}) - c]^2}{\bar{p}\bar{q} \sum_{j=1}^k n_j (x_j - \bar{x})^2} \sim \chi^2(1)$$

which is equivalent to

$$z = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^k y_j (x_j - \bar{x}) - c}{\sqrt{\bar{p}\bar{q} \sum_{j=1}^k n_j (x_j - \bar{x})^2}} \sim N(0,1)$$

$$n = \sum_{j=1}^k n_j \quad \bar{p} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^k y_j \quad \bar{q} = 1 - \bar{p} \quad \bar{x} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^k n_j x_j$$

Here, k is the number of columns in the corresponding $2 \times k$ contingency table, and c is an optional continuity correction factor. For each of the Cochran-Armitage tests performed in the present study, a 2×6 contingency table was constructed as illustrated in Table 3, with binary outcomes in two rows and 6 levels of predictor values in column. Training assessment scores were grouped into 6 bins ($k = 6$) labeled with x_j ($j = 1$ to 6) in an ascending order, with $x_1 = 1$ for the bin of 70-75 and $x_6 = 6$ for the bin of 96-100. y_j denoted the number of outcomes of interest (in the binary outcome variable Y) in a corresponding bin of assessment scores. n_j denoted the total counts of both opposing outcomes in column j . p and q denoted the observed response probabilities for opposing outcomes respectively.

Table 3: Schematic 2×6 Contingency Table

	$x_1=1$ (70-75)	$x_2=2$ (76-80)	$x_3=3$ (81-85)	$x_4=4$ (86-90)	$x_5=5$ (91-95)	$x_6=6$ (96-100)
$Y=1$	y_1	y_2	y_3	y_4	y_5	y_6
$Y=0$	$n_1 - y_1$	$n_2 - y_2$	$n_3 - y_3$	$n_4 - y_4$	$n_5 - y_5$	$n_6 - y_6$
Sum	n_1	n_2	n_3	n_4	n_5	n_6

5.1 Analysis of Random RI data

Among the four types of RI data (Random, Analytic, Supplemental, Rework), only the Random RI data were collected through a randomization process and could theoretically be considered representative of the production NRFU data. We thus first examined the association between the Random RI outcome and assessment score. However, we encountered a heavily skewed data set: About 60% of enumerators had only one Random RI case and 20% had only two cases, as shown in Figure 4. We thus used the outcome (Pass/Fail) of each enumerator's first RI case as his/her field performance indication for the following reasons: (1) Most enumerators had this very first RI case and therefore it covered almost the entire enumerator population; (2) no other more appropriate outcome measures could be identified. The major concern over this measure was its representativeness of an individual enumerator's overall performance because the outcome of a single RI case could heavily be influenced by chance. However, with a large number of the 1st random RI cases, such uncertainty would be diminished at the sample level.

Figure 4: Distribution of enumerators by number of Random RI cases.

The results of the Cochran-Armitage Trend Test showed that (1) enumerators performed generally well regardless of their assessment outcome (pass rate > 92%); (2) there was a positive association between the weighted total training assessment score and pass rate ($Z = -5.9, p < 0.0001$); (3) the magnitude of performance improvement with increase in assessment score appears small; (4) about 6% of enumerators with top scores (95-100) did not pass their first randomly-selected RI. Figure 5 depicts the trend of random RI pass rate over training assessment score.

Figure 5: Pass rate of the 1st randomly-selected RI case as a function of weighted assessment score.

5.2 Analysis of Analytic RI data

Analytic RI cases were selected based upon problematic behaviors detected in paradata or revealed in statistical calculations by the computer algorithm. The rationale for this analysis was that if the training had been effective, one would observe that fewer enumerators with higher training assessment score would be judged by the computer algorithm as having problematic behaviors. In this analysis, the predictor was weighted assessment score, which is the same as in the Random RI analysis. The outcome variable was percentage of enumerators with Analytic RI cases. Descriptive statistics suggested moderate upward trend in percent enumerators having Analytic RI cases with an increase in weighted training assessment score (Figure 6), which was confirmed by the *Cochran-Armitage Trend Test* ($Z = -3.9, p < 0.0001$). The finding does not support the hypothesis that the

higher the training assessment score, the less the percentage of enumerators with problematic behaviors. In fact, it shows a trend in the opposite direction.

Figure 6: Percentage of enumerators with Analytic RI case(s) in a 5-point bin of weighted training assessment score.

Figure 7: Percentage of enumerators with Supplemental RI case(s) in a 5-point bin of weighted training assessment score.

5.3 Analysis of Supplemental RI data

Supplemental RI cases were selected based upon problematic behaviors detected by human inspectors. Based on the same rationale as in the analysis on the analytic RI data, one would expect to observe a lower percentage of enumerators who were selected for Supplemental RI as training assessment score increased. In this analysis, the predictor was again the weighted assessment score. The outcome variable was percentage of enumerators with Supplemental RI cases. Descriptive statistics suggested a moderate downward trend in percent enumerators having Supplemental RI cases with an increase in weighted training assessment score (Figure 7), which was confirmed by the *Cochran-Armitage Trend Test* ($Z = 3.0, p = 0.0015$). In other words, enumerators with higher assessment scores were less likely to have cases selected for re-interview through the Supplemental Selection process. The results are consistent with the rationale, though the effect doesn't appear practically substantial.

5.4 Analysis of Rework RI data

When a RI case received a “Hard Fail” outcome, all other cases that were completed by the same enumerator but had not been re-interviewed yet were selected for RI, and consequently these cases were labeled as Rework RI. Based on the same rationale as in the analysis on the analytic RI data, one would expect to observe a lower percentage of enumerators who were selected for Rework RI as training assessment score increased. In this analysis, the predictor was again the weighted assessment score. The outcome variable was percentage of enumerators with Rework RI cases. Descriptive statistics showed a downward trend in percent enumerators having Rework RI cases with an increase in weighted training assessment score (Figure 8), which is confirmed by the *Cochran-Armitage Trend Test* ($Z = 6.0, p = 0.0001$), suggesting that enumerators with higher assessment scores were less likely to make Hard Fails.

Figure 8: Percentage of enumerators with Rework RI case(s) in a 5-point bin of weighted training assessment score.

5.5 Summary of Major Findings

To summarize, it was found in the present evaluation that (1) enumerators with training assessment scores of 70 or above generally performed NRFU well with pass rate of 92% or higher for the first randomly-selected RI case; (2) enumerators with higher training assessment scores performed slightly better than those with lower scores; (3) performance improvement associated with higher training assessment score was reflected on multiple measures: percent enumerators with passed 1st randomly-selected RI case, percent enumerators with a RI case through supplemental selection, and percent enumerators with a “Hard Fail” error; and (4) about 6% of enumerators with the highest training assessment scores did not pass the first randomly-selected RI.

6. Discussion

In the present study, we apply a multifaceted approach to generate convergent evidence from different data sources. We define one primary performance measure and three secondary performance measures for assessing NRFU field operations training effectiveness. Using multiple performance measures enables us to assess this type of training effectiveness from various aspects of the field operation and to reach a more comprehensive and robust measurement of training effectiveness. The outcomes from this training evaluation study show that our approach is effective and practically workable, particularly in the settings where the only data available are from production sources and with limitations around the data, such as skewed distributions, heterogenous data sources, etc.

It is crucial to acquire a comprehensive understanding of operational processes for a robust evaluation of a field training program. Such understanding helps the evaluation researchers design

an adequate evaluation plan, identify useful data sources, and define meaningful performance metrics. In the present study, we invested a substantial amount of time to review the operational documents, to interview stakeholders, and to revise the evaluation plan accordingly.

Statistical analysis is the central part of the evaluation. It is critically important to use statistical methods that fit the available data. In our original study plan, we intended to apply logistic regression to the binary outcome variable (“Pass” or “Fail”) and include covariates of interest. However, we later realized that logistic regression did not fit the data well. Consequently, we used the Cochran-Armitage Trend Test for the analysis.

In a separate study, the U.S. Census Bureau conducted another evaluation of the 2020 Census NRFU training (PTG International, 2021) at all four levels of the Kirkpatrick Model (Kirkpatrick & Kirkpatrick, 2006): Reaction, Learning, Behavior, and Results. That evaluation used questionnaires to collect self-reported information on reaction and behavior, and used Key Performance Indicators (e.g., average number of completed cases) based on production data to evaluate the training at the results level. Results from that evaluation are generally consistent with that of our study: Enumerators generally perform well, and their performance improves with higher assessment scores. In addition, our approach assesses training results from the perspective of outcome accuracy and utilized more refined data. A systematic literature review (Hope et al, 2024) found that the majority of training evaluations were performed at the reaction and learning levels, and few evaluations included the results level due to difficulties in collecting and analyzing data as well as expensive consumption of resources. However, evaluation researchers also recognize the benefit and importance of the results-level evaluation because it provides direct evidence of the effectiveness of training on the operation or organization (Alsalamah & Callinan, 2021). Our experience in the present evaluation of NRFU training echoes the existing literature. Further, our multifaceted approach to results-level training evaluation offers a methodological How-to to this body of literature.

Acknowledgments

This study was made possible through a collaborative effort by colleagues from various organizations at the U.S. Census Bureau. The authors would like to thank staff from these groups for their assistance in providing background information and data sources related to 2020 Census operations. These groups include the Center for Behavioral Science Methods; Field Division; Applications Development and Services Division; Decennial Census Management Division; and the Decennial Statistical Studies Division. In addition, the authors would like to thank Alfred D. Tuttle and Jon Krosnick for their insightful advice, and the following individuals for their helpful comments: Karen Deaver, Joanne Pascale, Paul Beatty, Nelson Er, Joanna Fane Lineback, Mikelyn Meyers, Christopher Stevenson, Jennifer Kim, Melissa Therrien, Jennifer Reichert.

Disclaimer

This paper is released to inform interested parties of research and to encourage discussion. The views expressed are those of the authors and not those of the U.S. Census Bureau. The paper has been reviewed for disclosure avoidance and approved under CBDRB-FY24-0425.

References

- Alsalamah, A., & Callinan C. (2021). Adaptation of Kirkpatrick’s Four-Level Model of Training Criteria to Evaluate Training Programmes for Head Teachers. *Education Sciences*, 11(3), 116. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci11030116>
- Armitage, P. (1955). Tests for Linear Trends in Proportions and Frequencies. *Biometrics*, 11 (3), 375–386. doi:10.2307/3001775. JSTOR 3001775.

- Cochran, W.G. (1954). Some methods for strengthening the common chi-squared tests. *Biometrics*, 10 (4), 417–451. doi:10.2307/3001616. JSTOR 3001616.
- Gibb, S., Le-Ammons, N., Garcia, C., Kraetsch, M., Kay, W., Brown, K., Adhikari, Y., Tau, M., Cleveland, R., Collins, K. (2023). *2020 Census Nonresponse Followup Operational Assessment Report*. U.S. Census Bureau, 2020 Census Evaluations and Experiments Report Series. Issued November 2023; Version 1.0. Available at: <chrome-extension://efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcglclefindmkaj/https://www2.census.gov/programs-surveys/decennial/2020/program-management/evaluate-docs/EAE-2020-nonresponse-followup.pdf>
- Hope, M., Hernandez, C., & Wang, L. (2024). *Evaluation of Field Operation Training Programs: A Systematic Review*. U.S. Census Bureau, Internal Report. Issued July 2024.
- Kirkpatrick, D., & Kirkpatrick, J. (2006). *Evaluating Training Programs: The Four Levels*. 3rd Edition. Berrett-Koehler Publishers.
- PTG International. (2021). *The U.S. Census Bureau - Field Training Evaluation Services 2020 Nonresponse Followup Census Training Evaluation Report*. U.S. Census Bureau, Internal Reported. Issued March 2021.
- Tau, M., Marquette, R.J., Dickson, T. (2023). *Nonresponse Followup Quality Assurance Results Report*. U.S. Census Bureau, 2020 Census Evaluations and Experiments Report Series. Issued August 2023; Version 1.0. Available at: <https://www.census.gov/programs-surveys/decennial-census/decade/2020/planning-management/evaluate/eac/2020-quality-results-report-nrfu.html>
- Tuttle, D., & Virgile, M. (2019). *2020 Nonresponse Followup Enumerator and Census Field Supervisor Training Final Assessments – Revised Weighting and Content Determination*. U.S. Census Bureau, Internal Memorandum. Issued October 2019.